

SONNET

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SONNET - SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

*Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions,
success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector*

D7.1: Co-creation, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI

Work Package: 7

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About SONNET

The SONNET project would like to make individuals and institutions from different disciplines put their work in common to try to understand the various ways in which things can change in society and how this can bring about innovations in the European energy sector or, on the contrary, prevent innovation from happening. It will look into how social innovation has already contributed to making our energy sources cleaner and how it could continue to help reduce our carbon footprint in the future.

Based on a range of already available sources and methods, which it will bring together for the first time, the project will try to find out what could help different kinds of social innovation in accelerating the transition from the use of fossil fuels to more renewables-based energy sources. However, it will also work with practical examples. To do this, project partners will work with so-called “City labs” in six European countries. Their participants will come from diverse disciplines and backgrounds. This way we will learn more about the many distinctive ways in which social innovation in the energy sector happens and contributes in practice to energy transitions that will remain valid in the long term. Moreover, SONNET will organise three surveys with citizens, on the ways they think things could be improved in the energy sector.

Last but not least, SONNET will combine the outcomes of its work in cooperation with all actors that were involved in the project, to explain how social innovation can contribute to the sustainable energy transition in Europe, taking into account different points of view. This information and recommendations will be widely disseminated through diverse communication channels, to reach as many concerned people as possible and allow them to benefit from the findings.

SONNET's Objectives

SONNET's overall aim is to generate new ways to understand the diversity, processes and contributions of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) and to critically evaluate and assess their success and future potential towards supporting sustainable transitions of energy systems. In order to achieve this aim, the following six objectives are pursued:

- **Objective 1: *Capture*** the diversity of social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) in Europe within a comprehensive SIE typology to allow for a differentiated analysis of SIE.
- **Objective 2: *Identify* and *analyse*** enabling and impeding conditions for SIE processes, with a focus on socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political issues and their interrelations with socio-technical aspects.
- **Objective 3: *Characterise*** the contributions of different types of SIE and their success to making energy more secure, sustainable, competitive and affordable for Europe's citizens by developing and applying a comprehensive SIE evaluation scheme.

- **Objective 4: Assess** the future potential of the SIE types identified as most effective in supporting the goals of the Energy Union and derive implications for reconfiguring existing and developing new business models for the identified market opportunities arising from these SIE.
- **Objective 5: Encourage** successful SIE through co-creating socio-political strategies to enhance governance arrangements and policy networks, as well as SIE-related power and policy dynamics.
- **Objective 6: Accelerate** sustainable energy transitions through trans-disciplinary co-creation of SIE in urban areas; a toolkit with practical recommendations for encouraging successful SIE; and capacity building activities for SIE actors, policy makers, academics, students and citizens.

PROJECT PARTNERS

N°	Participant name	Short Name	Country code	Partners' logos
1	Fraunhofer Institute of Systems and Innovation Research	ISI	DE	Fraunhofer ISI
2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble École de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Koźmińskiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zuercher Hochschule for Applied Research	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

The co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy of SONNET describes how the knowledge and experience of consortium partners will be used for communicating about the project, disseminating its results to a wide range of audiences and ensuring that the resulting ideas, methods and recommendations are taken up and continued to be used after the project ends (exploitation). Communication and dissemination activities (WP7) will be carried out from the very beginning (M1, June 2019) to the end of the project (M36, May 2022). The development of the strategy is led by ICLEI Europe, with the help of all partners. It will be updated systematically to ensure its continued alignment with the evolving SONNET project. In M20 (January 2021) an updated version of this document will be published (D7.2).

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1 *EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS*

1.1 Changes with respect to the DoA

This is the first version of SONNET's co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy. Its basic pillars were discussed with all project partners in an interactive lab at SONNET's first meeting from September 30 - October 2, 2019 in Karlsruhe. The strategy is intended to be a "living document", so it will be regularly updated as the project progresses. The current document contains no changes with respect to the DoA.

1.2 Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is intended to be used both by consortium partners to be clear about the co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy that was adopted at the outset of the project and what their role in it is. But also by external stakeholders interested in the project or social innovation in energy transitions in general.

1.3 Short Summary of results

As this is only the start of the project and the first in-person partner meeting just took place, no results are available for now.

1.4 Evidence of accomplishment

Evidence will be inserted here as soon as it becomes available.

2 INTRODUCTION

SONNET's co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy addresses three closely related issues:

1. How to **integrate** the knowledge and experience of all partners to improve quality and ensure the relevance of SONNET's results;
2. How to **share** SONNET's work and results with different stakeholders across Europe to attract their interest and maximise uptake;
3. How to ensure the **exploitation** of the results after the end of the project.

The strategy describes project target audiences, their needs in relation to the project, key messages to be shared with them and the most suitable channels to reach them. It also describes the general principles and specific formats to facilitate cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary learning, based on ICLEI's long-standing experience as a knowledge-broker between different actors in the field of sustainable energy, as well as based on input of all partners. Finally, the strategy includes a continuously updated plan for the exploitation and uptake of results.

2.1 Review of the communications environment

Strengthening the role of social innovation in energy transitions is a task that requires bringing different actors and types of knowledge together, reaching out to unusual suspects and breaking existing silos. This should result in the collaboration of different disciplines, such as social innovation and the energy sector (interdisciplinarity) and different societal actors, such as academia, practitioners and municipal representatives (transdisciplinarity) to arrive at new perspectives, orientations and possible solutions. Project activities target bridging the following silos in particular: (a) social innovation and energy domains, (b) SIE-initiatives and local governments, (c) new and old energy system actors, and (d) social and technological innovation. This bridge-building nature of the project is reflected both in its methodology and dissemination activities, which are designed from an inter- and transdisciplinary perspective, with special focus given to the needs of policy makers and practitioners, also bringing ideas from the local (city labs) to the European level.

2.1.1 Interdisciplinarity

SONNET aims to investigate how, to what extent and under which enabling conditions diverse types of SIE may result in new breakthroughs or successfully contribute to overcoming transition barriers, such as limited citizen engagement or slow adoption of new technologies. In order to achieve its overarching objective, SONNET will develop a novel interdisciplinary framework, which combines concepts and insights from three related fields of research: sustainability transitions research, energy research in social sciences and social innovation research.

SONNET’s unique contribution to this field of research is a systematic integration of insights and concepts from all three of these areas to tackle the question at hand. As a consequence, partners will need to use the appropriate tone and vocabulary when communicating about the project’s results, to make sure the contents reach and can be used by all intended target groups. For this reason during each project meeting some time will be dedicated to capacity-building for the consortium, to jointly discuss how best to communicate about the project and disseminate its results.

2.1.2 Transdisciplinarity

Given the issue and the close intertwinement of social, cultural, political, economic and technical themes, SONNET’s research work will be carried out in interdisciplinary collaboration with a trans-disciplinary composition and expertise of the consortium, which includes universities, research institutes, an international network and city administrations. The diverse backgrounds of SONNET project partners will ensure the quality of its results as well as their relevance to target cities and the wider audience of local governments interested in taking up its outcomes.

However, the meaningful inclusion of knowledge, feedback and contributions from a multitude of stakeholders spanning societal groups and actors also means that specific challenges not only for communication to the outside but also between the involved stakeholders might have to be overcome. This will make it necessary to use improved internal communication to bridge possible gaps between partners from different backgrounds and with varying working cultures. This plan therefore addresses the challenges of both internal and external communication.

Figure 1: SONNET partners and potential outreach through their respective networks

2.1.3 Co-creation of knowledge

SONNET is a research project. This means that its main results relate to new insights on the topic under investigation. However, it also covers the practical side by putting emerging insights into practice. The so-called City Labs approach is thereby central to SONNET. Project partners are working across six European countries with 30 SIE initiatives in six cities. They will also organise a number of face-to-face and on-line events to further validate and enrich its results. The project will co-create SIE activities and, in the process, encourage knowledge-sharing and learning between cities and associated partners. However, European countries and cities are diverse and therefore generic solutions can only have limited impact. The project is investing considerable resources in this co-creation process, as it will help translating its work into more relevant results and developing a sense of ownership among representatives of key target groups.

In this spirit of co-creation, some of SONNET's communications will take a more personal and informal tone. This will ensure that the project is approachable and invites co-creation of knowledge not only between partners, but also with input from other stakeholders. SONNET also aims to provide an innovative example of institutional dynamics needed to put SIE-initiatives at the core of the Energy Union, allowing them to take part in these processes.

3 CO-CREATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

3.1 Objectives

WP7 primarily contributes to SONNET Objective Six: Accelerate sustainable energy transitions through: transdisciplinary co-creation of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) in urban areas; a toolkit with practical recommendations for encouraging successful SIE; and capacity building activities for SIE actors, policy makers, academics, students and citizens. The specific objectives of WP7 are to:

- **Coordinate** the co-creation and dissemination process and develop a co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy, designed to share SONNET's results with a wide range of audiences (T7.1).
- **Build bridges** between sectors, disciplines and contexts by creating well-facilitated spaces for exchange and learning (T7.2), thereby:
 - Translating SONNET's results into actionable recommendations for policy makers and tools empowering SIE actors (T7.3),
 - Developing and disseminating novel and cutting-edge scientific knowledge about SIE (T7.4),
 - Contributing, upon invitation by the INEA, to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between H2020 supported actions.
- **Maximise** exploitation impact.

3.2 Target Groups

The project will prioritise the following target groups, recognising their key roles in accelerating energy transitions: Policy Makers, Practitioners, Researchers and Experts.

Project activities and results will also target other stakeholders essential to supporting the transition process, including:

With the support of project partners, special attention will be given to the stakeholders in the six SONNET cities, including citizens and community groups, politicians and civil servants, businesses and entrepreneurs, as well as local media outlets.

3.3 Key messages

To make sure to reach as wide an audience as possible, the project will use key messages, adapted to each of its target groups. Inputs on messages and slogans that partners find most appropriate for their and the project's audiences were elaborated during the first project meeting from 30 September to 2 October 2019, and are now being consolidated. They will be amended and developed during the course of the project, based on the consortium's experience with its implementation.

3.4 Communication strategy

3.4.1 Visual identity

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

The first step to an effective communication strategy is to create a coherent and pleasant visual identity for the project, so that it is unique and recognisable not only by its content but also by its appearance. This visual identity, including among others a project logo, document templates and presentation materials, will be easy to use for all partners to ensure clear communication to the outside. It will aim to connect energy and social innovation, using fitting colours, appropriate images and impactful graphical elements.

A call for designers has been published to request the support of a professional in the creation of a visual identity for SONNET, which will then be used by all partners for all project outputs. Initial ideas which will feed into the instructions to the selected designer have been discussed with consortium partners during the first F2F meeting on 30 September - 2 October 2019.

Guidelines on how to use the visual identity will be developed and WP leader ICLEI Europe will make sure that it is consistently used by partners throughout the duration of the project.

3.4.2 Communication channels

3.4.2.1 Project website

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

The website will be a public space for the project's communication efforts accessible to a large public (M6, MS13). It will be designed following the previously created visual identity and developed with SONNET's target audiences in mind. It will use an informal tone that invites readers in. It will also include reference to SONNET's academic outputs. In this way, an approachable tone, visual and easily understandable formats will be paired with more technical and formal results. The website will be initially developed in English. It is envisaged to translate the City lab pages into their respective languages, so that also materials accessible to a more local public can be uploaded.

The website will notably include:

- A home page with quick links to all relevant content, the latest news and events as well as a twitter feed;
- pages presenting the project, its goals and involved partners;
- a news and events section;
- a page presenting the City Labs (and possibly one per city lab in their respective language);
- one (or several) download area(s) with all materials and products developed in the framework of the project (including the toolkit, streamed project videos, factsheets, infographics, etc.);
- a "contact us" page.

The website will be maintained for at least 5 years after the project ends.

3.4.2.2 Social media

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

In order to reach out to as wide an audience as possible, SONNET will be using virtual communication channels, such as social media (M6, MS13). A dedicated **Twitter** account will be created as early as possible in the project to share information about its activities and results, as well as general information linked to SIE and related initiatives. The proposed handles discussed at the first SONNET meeting on 30 September - 2 October 2019 are @SONNET_transitions, @SONNET_energy, @SONNET_cities and @SONNET_socialinnovation, with an appropriate tagline such as "Social innovation for urban energy transitions" or "Social innovation in energy transitions". Based on the fruitful discussions with all consortium partners at the project meeting a consolidated proposal is now being developed.

A dedicated “channel” will be hosted on ICLEI Europe’s **YouTube** account, making use of its already existing reach to draw attention to the two videos to be produced in the framework of SONNET as well as webinar recordings for example.

Partners are encouraged to share this and other content on their own communication channels, such as, but not limited to: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, institutional websites, blogs or newsletters, to maximise the dissemination of project outcomes. **Social media guidelines** adapted to SONNET and its subject area will be developed and distributed amongst partners at the beginning of the project, to support them in maximising their use of those channels. An overview of partners existing communication channels and their potential outreach is shown in the annex.

3.4.3 Communication products

To further increase the outreach of its dissemination of results, SONNET will use different kinds of communication products, aimed at all of its target groups, such as a project leaflet and a series of practical recommendations. They will be available for download on the project website, publicised through the project’s and partners’ communication channels and a number of printed versions will be distributed at SONNET’s own and at events that will be attended by partners to share the project’s results.

3.4.3.1 Project Leaflet

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

A project leaflet will be developed on the basis of the visual identity elaborated in cooperation with a professional designer. It will be available both in electronic and print format and will be translated from English into the four languages of the project’s City labs (Polish, German, Flemish, French).

3.4.3.2 Practical recommendations and SIE Toolkit

Task 7.3, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by DRIFT and Fraunhofer ISI.

In order to facilitate the uptake of project results, SONNET will develop a mix of written and audio-visual practical recommendations to provide knowledge and tools to accelerate the energy transition, tailored to the needs of various target groups (i.e. practitioners and policymakers) (M10-M36). They will include the following types of tools:

- Five ‘**Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads**’ (M20-34, lead: ICLEI with the support of academic partners). These will take the form of short and accessible papers introducing main issues addressed by the project. They will distil main results and recommendations of the project from WP1-6, validated during WP7 events, and focus on the needs of different target groups. The issues to be addressed will be finalised during the project, but the preliminary proposed structure is the following:

- **#1 Social Innovation Meets Energy:** Introduction to the concept of social innovation and the roles SIE can play in accelerating energy transition, featuring examples from SONNET cities and the SONNET typology.
 - **#2 Social Innovation in Energy:** SIE city lab stories: summary of SONNET cities' experiences, describing lessons learned from the city labs and sharing their recommendations for other cities.
 - **#3 Social Innovation in Energy:** Socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political reflections: a set of empirical reflections outlining the interplay between socio-economic, socio-cultural (incl. gender) and socio-political issues of energy transitions and SIE, and their interplay with socio-technical factors; practical recommendations on how local, regional, national and European policy actors can encourage SIE to be able to address these issues.
 - **#4 Social Innovation in Energy Meets Europe:** How local SIE actors contribute to the achievement of European energy policy objectives and what kind of support (knowledge, funding and legislation) and enabling conditions are needed for local SIE working to enable sustainable energy transitions at the European level.
 - **#5 Social Innovation Has Met Energy:** Summary of SONNET results, easily accessible to practitioners and policy makers, serving as a navigation tool for all relevant project outputs.
- A series of five **infographics**, closely linked to the 'Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads', that summarise key project results in a visual way (M10-34, lead: ICLEI with the support of academic partners).
 - Two short **videos** (max. 3 minutes) - one introducing SONNET and the diversity of SIE (M12) and the other distilling key SONNET messages (M34) in a visual and accessible way. These will be uploaded to YouTube and subtitled in local languages (lead: ICLEI with the support of cities and respective academic partners).

On the basis of these practical outputs, SONNET will compile an **SIE Toolkit** (M34, lead: ICLEI with support of DRIFT), which will include:

1. the 'Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads';
2. the infographics;
3. a description of selected methods used within the project (e.g. the goal alignment map (T6.1), the typology of social innovations (T1.2) or methods to design and learn from experiments (T4.1 & T4.8));
4. the set of socio-political strategies for encouraging SIE (T2.1-T2.4).

This toolkit will be an open-access digital 'how-to-guide' available on SONNET's website with partners' websites referring to it, that describes in an accessible, non-academic language the steps needed to understand how different interests and institutions shape local energy systems and how to accelerate sustainable energy transitions, both from a single initiative perspective and a system perspective, illustrated with examples collected in WP1-6. It will include both the "what"

and the “how”, sharing methods used or developed within SONNET. The publication will be organised in a modular structure, allowing each user to decide how deep they want to go or what specific theme or city they want to follow. It will be promoted via a social media campaign to increase its audience. After the project, the toolkit will continue to be hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy and used as course material for training programmes developed as part of Task 7.4.

3.4.4 Bridging across the silos: face-to-face connections

Task 7.2, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by all partners, M5-M36.

In order to communicate about the project and facilitate the uptake of its results, SONNET will organise and/or participate in a series of relevant **events**, fostering face-to-face connections to bridge silos and to reach a diverse mix of stakeholders across all its target groups. They will be designed to bring together relevant actors and to foster a common understanding of the diversity, processes, successes and contributions, as well as future potential of SIE. For this, SONNET will pursue five event types:

- **#1: ‘Taking people-powered energy transitions from the local to the European level’** (M12, lead: ICLEI) - a Brussels-based 0.5-day event that addresses representatives of EU institutions and European networks and initiatives.
- **#2: A series of 12 local events on ‘Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition’** (M9-M26, Lead: city + academic partner with support from ICLEI) organised in each of the six SONNET cities (two per city) to officially launch and close each City Lab (WP4).
- **#3: Two ‘SONNET on Tour’ regional workshops** in the final stages of SIE city labs (M20-M26, lead: ICLEI with host cities and respective academic partners). These will be 1.5-day training workshops hosted by the SONNET cities Warsaw and Bristol. The workshops will prominently feature and include local SIE initiatives (e.g. field trips, peer learning sessions) and target local government representatives and SIE stakeholders.
- **#4: ‘Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition/Europe’** (M36, lead: ICLEI). This 1.5-day final conference in Antwerp will showcase the results of SONNET to a European audience and validate SONNET’s policy recommendations.
- **#5: Six ‘Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition’ webinars** (M5-M35, lead: ICLEI), held throughout the project, focusing on pertinent topics related to SIE and the energy transition. The recorded webinars will be shared via YouTube and promoted via the project and partners’ social media channels to reach additional audiences.

In addition to SONNET-organised events, the project will capitalise on the extensive networks of project partners and will present results at **selected national and European events**. A calendar of relevant events will be drawn up with the contribution of all partners and the project’s participation coordinated in the run-up to each event. As an example, SONNET will be featured during the 9th European Sustainable Cities and Towns Conference, which will be held in Mannheim in 2020.

3.4.5 Scientific outreach and training

Task 7.4, lead: UoS, co-lead: ISI, supported by: all academic partners and ICLEI, M6-M36.

To ensure that its methodologies, learnings and key results are shared across the variety of disciplines involved in SONNET and to reach out specifically to the scientific community, one of the project's target groups, also beyond project lifetime, this task envisages the following dissemination activities:

- **Participation in external conferences:** All partners will participate in the identification of relevant events in which the project can be presented, such as events organised by the European Commission, international conferences and workshops in the respective fields. Particularly relevant conferences for SONNET are, among others, the Behave conference; European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy, Energy and Society conference; Ecological Economics conferences; Environmental and Resource Economics conference; International Sustainability Transitions conference; European Association for the Study of Science and Technology conference; International Social Innovation Research conference; and the Living Knowledge conference.
- **Organisation of six special sessions at European and international conferences:** each academic partner will organise a special conference session to create visibility for the topic in different disciplinary and academic fields. We will actively seek to co-organise these special sessions with researchers from related European projects (e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts, and our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS).
- **Scientific journal publications and working papers:** Partners are encouraged and assisted in publishing project results in peer-reviewed journals and working paper series to ensure broad visibility to the scientific community. SONNET consortium members will publish through appropriate open access schemes, including as pre-publication in institutional working paper series (e.g. Fraunhofer ISI Working Papers, SPRU Working Paper Series) and upload postprints in university repositories.
- **Guest-editing a Special Issue on Social Innovation in Energy Transitions:** Based on a Call for Papers which we will initiate, we will invite submissions from relevant academics doing work on SIE (including colleagues from other EU projects e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts, and our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS). Following a competitive selection process, a two-day workshop organised by UoS discussing the invited contributions will allow for in-depth mutual learning and exchange of experience and lead to a collaborative output in form of a special issue in a peer reviewed scientific journal (e.g. Energy Policy, Energy Research and Social Science, Research Policy).
- **Integration of SONNET results into academic teaching and practical training programmes:** University Partners will integrate SONNET findings into their teaching materials for students at all levels and seek to involve Masters' dissertations and PhD theses in the work of SONNET. In addition, DRIFT will produce a SONNET training module to be included in their Transition Academy Courses (e.g. their Masterclass 'Energy Transition') targeted at practitioners and policy makers. Also, ICLEI will use SONNET findings in their network trainings.

3.4.6 Related projects and initiatives

To maximise outreach and increase the sharing of knowledge and experiences, SONNET will be in contact with related Horizon 2020 projects. This will include projects funded under the same call as SONNET (our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS) and other energy- or social innovation-related projects (e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts).

Project partners also have long-standing experience working on social innovation and/or energy transitions and are actively involved in relevant European and global networks that gather researchers, local government representatives or social innovation frontrunners (e.g. Global Covenant of Mayors, EU Urban Agenda, ECOLISE, Social Innovation Exchange, International Sustainability Transitions Network, Eu-SPRI and others). This ensures that SONNET results will not only be widely shared, but will also feed into ongoing and future policy processes.

4 EVALUATION AND MONITORING

The WP leader (ICLEI) will be in charge of monitoring and evaluating all activities of the project mentioned in this strategy. This includes monitoring the overall communication, but also keeping track of dissemination done by partners at a local to international level. The impact of those activities will be assessed, as well as how well they serve the project objectives and if they suitably reach their target audiences. The monitoring and evaluation process will be threefold:

- **Internal:** All communication activities will be compiled and the target reach analysed. Statistics from the website and document download history will tell us more about the most-used items and which areas of the website are potentially not (yet) optimised (number of visits, time spent on the website, where visitors are from, share of returning visitors, number of downloads, etc.). Social media statistics will shed light on the content that is most liked, shared and by whom (number of Twitter followers, tweets, impressions; views of YouTube videos, etc.). The KPIs will be used to evaluate the success of communication and dissemination efforts. Evaluation forms will be distributed after each project-related event to get qualitative feedback.
- **External:** ICLEI Europe will develop a dissemination tracking tool where each partner reports after each communication activity (publication of an article, blog, press release, attendance or organisation of an event, etc.) what was done, how many people were reached, divided by target groups aimed at (as requested by the Commission) and a link to “evidence”. All partners are responsible for filling in the tracking tool after every activity they implement, to monitor and report on all the project's activities. Compiling this information in the monitoring form will give all partners a solid perspective on target outreach.
- **Mid-term evaluation:** This strategy will itself be revised and updated at the midpoint of the project (M20, January 2021, D7.2) to assess the efficiency and impact of its messages and channels.

5 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

To make it easier to assess the effectiveness of its communication and dissemination strategy, a series of key performance indicators was elaborated. They are described in the table below:

Table 1: Overview of selected quantifiable target indicators to measure impact

Selected diss. & com. activities and their impacts	Indicator	Target Value (M18/M36)	Task
Website	Unique views per month	500/1000	T7.1
Twitter	Followers	300/600	T7.1
YouTube channel	Total views	400/800	T7.3
People reached in SONNET cities	Number of people per urban area studied (x6)	500/1000 (3000/6000)	T7.2
People reached via European events	People attending events organised by SONNET and others	150/500	T7.2, T7.3
Policy makers who participated in events, research activities or engagement	3 @ 6 SONNET cities, 10 @ 8 countries, 20 @ EU level	30/118	T5.5, WP2, 4, 7 in general
Local co-creators and stakeholders from science, society, policy and business involved directly in engagement process in their urban area	People per SONNET city and surrounding region	40 (240)	T4.2 - T4.7
Stakeholder from science, society, policy and business attending webinars	Attendees @ webinar	100 (600)	T7.2
Stakeholders from science, society, policy and business attending final SIE conference	N° of attendees	100	T7.2
Share of participants of SONNET-organised events rating the content as useful for their daily work	Share based on event evaluation survey	70%	T7.2
Participants from Eastern and Central Europe	Share across SONNET events	20%	T7.2
Downloads of SONNET Energy Reads	Number of downloads	100/300	T7.3
Articles about SONNET published outside the project website	Number of articles	5/10	T7.1-7.4
Academics aware of the project activities and findings through at least 10 conference presentations plus 10 scientific papers submitted during project period (2 per academic partner) and 1 special issue guest-edited	Academics reached by each of the six academic partners through Research Gate, working papers online, conference presentations, etc.	100/250 (600/2250)	T7.4
Project partners experienced and trained in transdisciplinary co-creation	2 people per SONNET city (x6) plus 3 per other partners (x 7)	33	WP 2, 4 & WP 7 in general
Potential future SIE city labs generated from this project	10 from each of the two regional workshops	20	T7.2

6 TIMELINE

7 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION AND RESPONSIBILITIES

7.1 Communication amongst project partners

As mentioned at the beginning of this strategy, due to the trans-disciplinary nature of SONNET, its success will strongly rely on the quality of the communication and cooperation between its twelve full and an additional associated partner (city of Basel). It gathers stakeholders ranging from universities and research institutes to municipalities and NGOs. In practice, internal communication between partners will be maintained throughout the project by on-line and in-person meetings, as well as regular e-mail exchanges. Internal communication channels are arranged in such a way that they are efficient, effective and tailored to project needs. This includes a range of different communications means and mechanisms, from face-to-face contacts, project meetings, to online meetings, telephone contact or teleconferences. An online knowledge management system is provided from WP8 to facilitate collaborative writing and collection, sharing, reviewing, commenting and discussing of results and other project information. On some occasions, physical meetings will coincide with international workshops, to save costs.

7.2 Distribution of responsibilities

All consortium partners have a leadership position, with each academic partner and ICLEI leading a WP, and each city partner leading their city lab task (with the exception of Basel, who joins SONNET as an associated partner).

ICLEI is in charge of the editorial and publication responsibility of all communication and dissemination products, including the project Website, social media accounts, brochure and final report, among others. It will provide all partners with the project's visual identity and guidelines on how to use it, but also promotional material and templates for documents and presentations.

Project partners are responsible for communication and dissemination on a national and local level. This includes:

- **Local webpage:** Each consortium partner must have information about the project on their website, with key information in the local language, and a link to the SONNET Website.
- **Sharing:** Partners will maximise the outreach of the project by sharing the communications on their own channels (web, social media, interest groups...).
- **Media:** Project partners will be responsible for national and local media engagement, using their contacts to promote the project to the national and local targets.
- **Events:** Partners will present the project and its findings at relevant events or conferences.
- **Monitoring:** All consortium partners will keep a record of all activities for evaluation and monitoring purposes through the template provided by ICLEI.

8 USE OF RESULTS AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

To ensure that the impacts of this work will continue after the project has been completed, SONNET will put in place the following:

- **Exploitation Roadmap:** A roadmap will be drafted for the exploitation of SONNET's results, which will be included in the updated co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy, expected in M20. The roadmap will be elaborated during the second half of the project, with a focus on different scenarios for long-term maintenance and development of project results and uptake by various beneficiaries of its impact. To assess the different possible scenarios, the intervening relevant users and stakeholders in the field will be encouraged to provide feedback. This exploitation roadmap will include the definition of a structure for spreading results and a roadmap of actions to be undertaken after the project ends. It will also include a plan to engage new communities, strengthen outputs through new projects and initiatives, and disseminate and demonstrate the benefits of the approach to policy makers and society at large.
- **Migration of SONNET toolkit:** After the end of the project, the 'SIE toolkit' will be hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy and used as course material for training programmes developed as part of SONNET (T7.4). Thereby, this toolkit will continue to support SIE actors, policy makers, businesses and citizens to understand how different interests and institutions shape local energy systems and how to accelerate energy transitions.
- **Maintenance of project website:** Through the maintenance of the project website for at least 5 years after the project has finished, its outputs and partners will continue to be easily searchable and accessible for clarification, advise, networking or evaluation services. In addition, key outputs will be made available on partners' websites and repositories, so that they remain accessible beyond the lifetime of the project website.
- **Nomination of post-project contact points:** SONNET's PI will continue to serve as a main contact point for all SONNET related requests and will also nominate one contact point for each partner country. These will remain available beyond the lifetime of the project for knowledge transfer to interested stakeholders, such as policy makers, local administrations, think tanks, media and citizens. It will be made clear at dissemination events that further contact is possible, as well as interest in supporting new projects and initiatives.

Appendix

Overview of partners' already existing social media channels

Table 2: Overview of partners' already existing social media channels.

Partner	Channel	Potential outreach (followers, subscribers, etc.)
Fraunhofer ISI	Twitter <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://twitter.com/FraunhoferISI • https://twitter.com/Fraunhofer_KA 	~1,300
	YouTube <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Channel of Fraunhofer ISI • Channel of the 3 Fraunhofer Institutes in Karlsruhe 	~50 ~250
	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/fraunhoferisi	~5,000
DRIFT	Twitter: https://twitter.com/drifteur	~4,700
	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/driftfortransition/	~900
	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/5261542/	~1,700
SPRU	Twitter: https://twitter.com/SPRU	~9,996
	Sussex Energy Group Twitter: https://twitter.com/sussexnrggroup/	~4,055
	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/uniofsussex	~87,000
	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/sussexuni/	~29,500
	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCla0VPygMxQx4iyz11OfxIw	~315
Vimeo: https://vimeo.com/uniofsussex	~4,430	
GEM	Twitter: https://twitter.com/grenoble_em	~15,700
	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/GrenobleEM/	~49,000
	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/grenoble_em/	~8,000
	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjA22pgPEWtIfTBiZunsW4g	~20,200
	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/grenoble-ecole-de-management/	~57,842
ALK	Twitter: https://twitter.com/KozminskiUni	~1,500
	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/kozminski	~29,000
	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/kozminskiuniversity/	~6,000
	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/wwwkozminskiedupl	~1,300
	Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/kozminskiuni/albums	~15
	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/akademialeonakozminskiego/	~36,000
ZHAW	Twitter: https://twitter.com/zhaw	~6,200
	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/zhaw.ch	~7,700
	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/zhaw/	~4,700
	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/ZHAWch	~260

	<p>LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/z-rcher-hochschule-f-r-angewandte-wissenschaften-zhaw-</p> <p>Xing: https://www.xing.com/companies/z%C3%BCrcherhochschulef%C3%Bcrangewandte-wissenschaften</p> <p>Issuu: https://issuu.com/zhaw</p>	<p>~20,500</p> <p>n.n.</p> <p>~40</p>
ICLEI	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/ICLEI_Europe</p> <p>Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/iclei_europe/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/icleieurope</p>	<p>~15,300</p> <p>~30</p> <p>~260</p>
MANN	<p>Newsletter / Bürgerbrief: https://web.inxmail.com/mannheim/buergerbrief.jsp</p> <p>Feeds: https://www.mannheim.de/de/rss-feeds</p> <p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/StadtverwaltungMannheim</p> <p>Mediathek: https://www.mannheim.de/de/mediathek</p> <p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/mannheim_de</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/StadtMannheim</p> <p>Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mannheim_de/</p>	<p>n.n.</p> <p>n.n.</p> <p>~7,000</p> <p>n.n.</p> <p>~1,800</p> <p>~600</p> <p>~4,300</p>
ANTW	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/visitantwerp</p> <p>Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/antwerpen/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/visitantwerpen</p> <p>Pinterest: https://nl.pinterest.com/visitantwerp/</p>	<p>~33,500</p> <p>~37,200</p> <p>~500</p> <p>~40</p>
BRIS	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/bristolcouncil</p> <p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/BristolCouncil</p> <p>Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/bristolcouncil/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/bristolcitycouncil</p> <p>Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/bristolcouncil</p>	<p>~103,000</p> <p>~7,900</p> <p>~1,740</p> <p>~665</p> <p>~148</p>
GREN	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/i/web/status/1172100409147699200</p> <p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/149306629191/posts/10157377882099192/</p> <p>Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/villedegrenoble/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/villedegrenoble</p>	<p>~40,000</p> <p>~168,000</p> <p>~18,400</p> <p>~700</p>
WARS	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/warszawa</p> <p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/warszawa/</p> <p>Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/fall_in_love_with_warsaw/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/warszawapl</p>	<p>~270,000</p> <p>~234,000</p> <p>~72,900</p> <p>~16,100</p>